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Abstract:

This deliverable report summarizes the performance studies of the first Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (DMAPS) prototypes, which primarily target excellent position resolution (high granularity), carried out in the first period of the project. Each effort resulted in one or more publications highlighted in the report.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2023

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

The production and initial tests of several Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (DMAPS) using different CMOS technologies that primarily target excellent position resolution (high granularity) have been successfully performed and included in the AIDAinnova Milestone report MS18 [1]. This report presents the characterization of these prototypes that resulted in one or more publications (highlighted in the report).

The TJ-Monopix2 and MALTA2 are two full size, matured devices, that are being characterized in the context of the AIDAinnova WP5 activities. The very encouraging first results obtained before and after irradiation are summarized below [2, 3].

DMAPS fabricated on technologies with smaller feature sizes are a natural path to achieving high granularity. The Tower (TJ) foundry has been chosen to evaluate the first prototypes on 65 nm. A first multi-layer reticle that includes pixel test structures was fabricated. The initial performance studies, which included charge collection measurements using radiation sources, were performed [4].

DMAPS exploiting both tracking and timing domains are being explored for future experiments. Within this work package, an early prototype in the LFoundry 150 nm process, called Mini-Cactus, has been fabricated. The first promising results [5] are included in this report.

These activities constitute unique advances in the effort to bring the DMAPS solutions to the next generation of High Energy Physics experiments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Detectors (DMAPS) are a key technology for the AIDAinnova project as they constitute the most interesting new direction of pixel detector development and are, therefore, a fundamental approach for present and planned accelerator experiments.

The WP5 activities branch into two main lines, one focusing on high granularity devices, targeting above all high position resolution, the other targeting foremost high radiation hardness. The production and initial tests of several high-granularity DMAPS (prototype 1) are documented in the AIDAinnova Milestone report MS18 [1]. The current Deliverable Report presents the characterization of those prototypes that resulted in one or more publications.

This Report includes the characterization of the following prototype 1 devices:

1. TJ-Monopix2 and TJ-MALTA2 DMAPS sensors in the 180 nm CMOS technology
2. Prototypes for exploration of the 65 nm CMOS technology
3. Mini-Cactus prototypes in the 150 nm CMOS technology

Each section below summarizes the main results of these efforts, followed by the conclusions and outlook.

2 LARGE CMOS PIXEL ARRAYS IN TOWER-JAZZ 180 NM TECHNOLOGY (TJ-MONOPIX2 AND TJ-MALTA2)

The development of Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel sensors has followed two generally different design approaches (Fig. 1): (a) large electrode design and (b) small electrode design. While within AIDAInnova (a) is the prime approach for high radiation hardness, (b) targets primarily high granularity, i.e. small pixels, and low-noise and low-power operation, albeit with good radiation tolerance as well. Deliverables of designs (b) is the theme of this report. The low-noise/low-power is due to the small charge collection electrode, which yields a small capacitance at the amplifier input. On the other hand, charge collection (signal) is more challenging, particularly under operating conditions that cause radiation damage to the structures, as is the case at the LHC. Therefore, the development focuses on achieving radiation-tolerant full charge collection and large signal-to-noise ratio for high hit-detection efficiency.

Fig. 2.1 Two approaches for DMAPS: (a) large electrode cell design, (b) small electrode cell design.

The two large area chips TJ-MALTA2 (1x2 cm²) and TJ-Monopix2 (2x2 cm²) are developed in 180 nm technology offered by Tower Semiconductor (Israel) and have common front-ends (charge collecting structure and readout amplifier) [1]. Both chips are fabricated on a common reticle. The difference rests in the architecture of the pixel readout: while TJ-Monopix1/2 employs an established column-drain-type readout architecture, TJ-MALTA1/2 features a challenging low-power asynchronous readout needing GHz synchronization. The otherwise very successful production of the Monopix1/MALTA1 prototypes showed an efficiency drop in pixel corners after irradiation which was intensively studied by interim prototyping (miniMALTA) to cure this problem.

Fig. 2.2: Photographs of successfully produced TJ-Monopix2 (left) and TJ-MALTA2 (right).

The cure of this efficiency drop was the focus for version 2 of both chips. The measures taken are:

- reshaping the charge collection path by increasing the lateral electric field for better Q-collection;
- improvement of the first stage of the readout electronics for lower noise (primarily suppression of RTS noise) and lower threshold operation;
- an increase of the depletion depth by employing Czochralski (Cz) material as substrate wafer rather than using epitaxial Si.

The TJ-Monopix2/MALTA2 chips were successfully delivered in 2021, see [1]. The measures were successful and solved the efficiency problem of the predecessor versions. Fig. 2.3 shows examples of the successful reduction of RTS noise and the obtained high efficiency after irradiation.

Fig. 2.3: (left) RTS noise reduction in TJ-MALTA2 compared to TJ-MALTA2. (right) Efficiency measured after irradiation (MALTA2).

The obtained noise is low indeed. The minimum threshold (from >300 e- to 200 e-) and threshold dispersion (from 30e- to 10e- after tuning) were improved according to specs. Fig. 2.4 shows the excellent noise and threshold performance of TJ-Monopix2 (before irradiation).

Fig. 2.4: (left) Noise ($rms = 6e^-$) and (right) threshold dispersion ($rms \approx 3e^-$) in TJ-Monopix2.

Figure 2.5 shows signal spectra to minimum ionising particles of TJ-DMAPS version using epi-Si and Cz material as detecting substrates in comparison. The signal charge is sufficiently large above the threshold, especially for the Cz material, such that highly efficient operation can be expected

Fig. 2.5:(left) Noise ($rms = 6e^-$) and (right) threshold dispersion ($rms \approx 3e^-$) in TJ-Monopix2 (before irradiation).

The characterizations are ongoing. Next, more efficiency studies with irradiated samples in test beams are planned. The results of the characterization of these devices are described in detail in reference [2, 3].

3 PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT IN TOWER-JAZZ 65 NM TECHNOLOGY (TJ65)

As mentioned above, exploring technologies with smaller feature sizes potentially offer interesting advantages in terms of better position resolution and radiation hardness. The 65 nm TPSCo (Tower Jazz or TJ) process is currently being investigated in the context of the AIDAInnova and CERN frameworks by a large consortium as a potential technological candidate for the design of sensors to be used in various future detectors, the closest in time being the ALICE-ITS3 project.

The first exploratory submission in 65 nm TPSCo was documented in [4]. It included the CE-65 detector family designed to explore the charge collection properties of this process. It comprises of chips featuring two-pixel pitches (15 and 25 μm) and various sensing node geometries. Two of these structures, called basic and optimized diodes, with 15 μm pitch were evaluated. The first variant implements a standard small collection well, being a reference sensing diode structure. The optimized diode is a modification that targets the development of a lateral electric field at the pixel edges to improve charge collection. In both cases, the reverse biasing of the sensing node is obtained through the front side by applying a positive potential directly to the collection electrode and keeping the substrate grounded. Different readout flavours have also been implemented: both a source follower (SF) with gain below one, and an amplifier with gain (AMP) of about five have been used, both in a version where the sensor is DC coupled to the readout input, and in an AC coupled version inserting a custom metal to metal capacitor. Further details of the structure designs and readout architecture can be found in [4].

The prototype performance was studied in the laboratory using radiation sources. Figure 3.1 (left) presents the iron source spectrum of single-pixel clusters from the optimized diode. The spectrum confirms the low pixel noise and points to a promising energy resolution.

The effect of changing the depleting region can be explored in AC-coupled devices, while in the DC structures this is more problematic, as varying the bias voltage can result in shifts in the electronics' operating points. The Fe-55 peak position with respect to the applied biasing voltage is shown in Fig. 3.1 (left). Focusing on the results for AC-AMP, one observes that for both diodes' geometries the charge collection (and thus the depletion region) increases to about 5 V where a plateau is reached. One can also observe that at higher reverse biases, the signal amplitude is comparable for the standard and optimized sensor, while at lower biases the amplitude degenerates faster for the optimized sensor due to a faster increase of the sensor capacitance (due to the enlargement of the depleting region). No meaningful conclusions could be made for sub-matrices DC-AMP and DC-SF, for which the biasing voltage is fixed by design. One could, however, notice that the ratios between optimized and basic structures are preserved. The differences in gain between sub-matrices also agree with the simulations, showing that DC-AMP has about 5 times higher gain than DC-SF while for the AC versions, it is only 3 times higher (due to parasitics introduced by the separation capacitance).

Fig. 3.1. Left: Iron source spectrum of single pixel clusters from the optimized diode. Right: Evolution of the Fe peak signal amplitude as a function of the reverse bias voltage across the sensing node for the various CE-65 pixel structures. Both plots are from reference [4].

More complex structures were also included in this first production run, including the Digital Pixel Test Structure (DPTS), which performance is being systematically studied. Figure 3.2 (left) shows the pixel cross section. A deep n-type implant was introduced to displace the junction from the collection diode into the epitaxial layer and thus increase the depletion region. Following what was studied in simpler structures above, this is expected to accelerate the charge collection and reduce charge sharing to give more operating margin due to the larger seed pixel signal.

Each pixel in the DPTS implements a high gain cascoded inverting amplifier followed by a discriminator and a reset circuit. Figure 3.2 (right) shows a photograph of the DPTS taken under a microscope. Starting from the centre and going outwards, the pixel matrix, shift register block, guard rings, and bonding pads can be distinguished.

Fig. 3.2. Left: Pixel cross section, not to scale. Right: photo of the DPTS chip.

The DPTS devices, which also feature a pixel pitch of 15 μm , were irradiated to fluencies of $1\text{E}15$ $n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ and tested with a beam at CERN's SPS accelerator complex. Initial results indicate that a low threshold can be achieved and that the devices provide an excellent position resolution (about 4 μm), see Fig. 3.3.

Fig. 3.3. Spatial resolution of DPTS devices irradiated to different fluencies as a function of the chip threshold. For lower threshold the cluster size increases, as expected, while the position resolution

Of course, further studies of these devices are ongoing. In parallel, the next submission of DMAPS chips and structures in 65 nm has been submitted. Measurements on these devices will be reported in a subsequent report.

4 PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT IN LFOUNDRY 150 NM TECHNOLOGY (MINI-CACTUS)

DMAPS exploiting both tracking and timing domains are an attractive option for future experiments. Within this work package, an early prototype in the LFoundry 150 nm process called Mini-Cactus has been fabricated to explore this possibility. It features distinct matrices with various pixel sizes (1 mm to 50 μm), low power consumption and fast peaking times. The fabrication of the chip was already reported in [5].

Mini-Cactus is a monolithic CMOS sensor demonstrator designed for time tagging individual Minimum Ionizing Particles with an accuracy better than 100 ps [5]. The sensor features an active array of 2×4 pixels surrounded by guard rings used to bias the high-resistivity substrate, an analog and digital front-end per pixel, a slow control interface and internal programmable biases through DACs. The baseline pixel sizes are 1.0 mm² and 0.5 mm². The sensing element is a deep n-well/p-substrate diode without internal amplification. The analog front-ends and the discriminators for each pixel have been implemented outside the pixel, at the column level. After fabrication, the sensors were thinned to 200 μm and 100 μm and then post-processed for backside biasing. As such, this sensor is a demonstrator chip for future large-scale timing detectors, like upgrades of timing detectors at LHC, or future high energy physics detector projects.

The Mini-Cactus Front-End (FE) circuit (Fig 4.1) is implemented outside of the pixel, at the column level. This way, the metallization over the pixel diode due to the power lines has been avoided. The FE architecture is based on a fast CSA (Charge Sensitive Amplifier) followed by a leading-edge discriminator. Bias currents, feedback current, discriminator threshold, enabling logic and other parameters are programmable via internal DACs. Output analog and digital buffers are shared among all the pixels on the same column.

Fig. 4.1. Architecture of the MiniCACTUS Front-End.

The MiniCACTUS chip features two outputs per column: an LVDS signal, a buffered version of the FE discriminator outputs and a monitoring signal, a buffered version of the CSA signals. Several pixel flavours have been implemented in Mini-Cactus. The targeted pixels have sizes of 1 mm \times 1 mm and 0.5 mm \times 1 mm. The FE has been optimized for these pixels with a peaking time of 1 ns. After fabrication, some detectors were thinned to 100 or 200 μm .

The devices were tested before irradiation with electrons from a Sr-90 source. A PMT located after the devices under test (DUTs) provides the reference signals. The signals from the prototype and the PMT are recorded with an oscilloscope. Only the electrons depositing energy in coincidence in the Mini-Cactus DUT and the PMT are taken into account. This ensures the selection of high

energy \square electrons with characteristics close to MIPs. The resulting energy spectrum in the DUT is Landau-like, see Fig 4.2 (left).

Fig. 4.2. Right: Amplitude distribution of the analog monitoring output of MiniCACTUS obtained with Sr-90 source (for a 200 μm -thick sensor). Left: Time resolution of the PMT+Mini-Cactus measured with the Sr-90 source after time walk correction.

The distribution of the time difference between the time of arrival of the \square electrons in the PMT and the MiniCACTUS gives access to the quadratic sum of the PMT time resolution and the Mini-Cactus time resolution. Once time walk effects are corrected for and if we consider only \square electrons yielding a signal height similar to the one we obtained for MIPs, we find that the quadratic sum of the PMT time resolution and the MiniCACTUS chip is 139.2 ± 1.4 ps. Separately, the MIP amplitude spectrum and time resolution of the PMT using cosmic muons detected in coincidence in two identical PMTs and scintillators were measured. From this, one can deduce a PMT time resolution for MIPs of 110 ps. After subtraction of the 110 ps PMT resolution from 139.2 ± 1.4 ps, we obtain an 85.3 ± 0.85 ps resolution for Mini-Cactus. This is an encouraging first result [5].

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS

The first results of the characterization of the high granularity DMAPS (prototypes 1) and the first device for timing applications were presented. The TJ-Monopix2 and the TJ-MALTA2 large size devices offer excellent results in terms of operational points (threshold and noise) and efficiency before (Monopix2) and before and after (MALTA2) irradiation. These are two of the most advanced developments worldwide, resulting in experiment ready devices with full readout architecture. Further performance results of these prototypes after irradiation will follow.

The first results of DMAPS structures and simple devices in the 65 nm technology were completed. This is the first time such technology has been investigated for HEP. The results are very encouraging and the activities continue to evolve.

In parallel, the first results of a DMAPS targeting sub 100 ps time resolution were summarized. The preliminary results already indicate that the target time resolution can be achieved, and improvements are expected to be made in a subsequent submission to optimize the front-end amplifier further.

The ARCADIA effort, not included in this report, will be documented in the next deliverable, since the results were not matured at the time of the writing of this report.

6 REFERENCES

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NOTE: for a full list of the AIDAinnova WP5 publications, please see the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/aidainnova-project/search?page=1&size=20&keywords=WP5>.

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
DMAPS	Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors